

ADEAGBO Mathew Oluwaseun Ph.D.

Department of Economics, Oyo State College of Education, Lanlate

Email: oadeagbomathew@yahoo.com, mathewoa@oyscoel.edu.ng

Phone: 08034943882

Abstract

Nigerian government has consistently claimed an increased spending year in year out as reflected in the country's increased annual budget that has metamorphosed from the level of millions of naira to billions of naira and postulating to trillions of naira. Unfortunately, the rising government expenditure has not translated to improved citizens' welfare as many Nigerians have continued to wallow in abject poverty, while more than 50 percent live on less than US\$2 per day indicating that the country's inhabitant has been feeling poorer in terms of their welfare which also reflected in the persistent human development challenges. This study thus examined the true effect of government expenditure on Nigerian inhabitant's welfare using annual time series data spanning 1980-2024. The study employed the use of ARDL modelling approach to analyze the data collected due to the mixed order of the variables employed as confirmed by the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test after carrying out other robustness tests such as ARDL Bound testing which confirm the existence of long-run equilibrium relationship among the employed variables. The long-run results from the study revealed that all variables employed presents a positive and statistically significant influence on Human Development Index (HDI) except inflation which negatively affects HDI, reducing the welfare effect of government spending on the inhabitants. Considering the short-run effect, the result from the error correction term, which is correctly signed and significant, indicates that approximately 64% of the short-run disequilibrium is corrected annually. The study thus concludes that allocation of public expenditure towards critical sectors remain an essential ingredient for improving human development outcomes in Nigeria. It was therefore recommended, among others, that improved government expenditure on education, health, transport and communication as well as agriculture should be sustained while effective monetary and fiscal policies to keep inflation at bay and improves citizens' welfare should be put in place.

Keywords: *Government Expenditure, Human Development Index, Nigeria, Welfare.*

Introduction

Public expenditure globally plays a crucial role in the promotion and enhancement of the overall human capital development and entire citizen's well-being, especially that of the inhabitants of third world countries which are faced with significant challenges of rising poverty, income inequality, and limited access to basic infrastructural facilities that brings about improved living standard (Singh & Chudasama, 2020; Bhanumurthy, et.al., 2018). Government spending on key welfare providing services; such as education, healthcare, social infrastructural facilities, affordable housing estates, and agricultural sector; not only contributes to economic prosperity but also ensure improved quality of life for their citizens.

Saini and Mahender (2023) as well as Samuel and Oruta (2021) in their related studies have also affirmed that government spending on key welfare services have the potential of reducing poverty, fostering social welfare, and as well create positive outcomes for individuals and the society as a whole.

From the above submission, one will see that in spite of the fact that a major goal of every government is the growth and development of the economy they govern. Nevertheless, it is still imperative for them to align social security measures with the country's growth rate to ensure development through sustainable human development. Neglecting to provide adequate welfare support as the economy expands can impede progress in human development and jeopardize the government aim of economic growth and development. Fostering human development and overall well-being of the citizen through effective government spending is thus an imperative concern.

Over the years, government expenditure has been on the increase, as reflected in the yearly budget. Government even embarks on various development strategies and policy frameworks to ameliorate the suffering of the citizens and improve their welfare. Some of the various government welfare packages, over years, include the pre-independence and early independence packages (Extended family support systems, Community development programmes, Missionary schools and Hospitals, public education expansion and basic public health services), the Structural Welfare Programmes between 1980s and 1999 (Operation Feed the Nation, Green Revolution Programme, Directorate of Food, Roads, and Rural Infrastructure, National Directorate of Employment, etc). Of recent government introduced National Home-Grown School Feeding Programme, Fuel Subsidy (1970s-2023), Conditional Cash Transfers, Government Enterprise and Empowerment Programme (2016), National Housing Fund, Pension and Social Security Schemes, COVID Palliatives, Subsidy Palliatives, and many more.

Despite these numerous development strategies and spending frameworks adopted over years, Nigeria continues to contend with some optimal outcomes from public expenditures as manifested in rising poverty rate and low economic growth. The substantial amount of annual public spending (as shown statistically in annual budget) is expected to have improved welfare indicators and economic efficiency in Nigeria. However, the contrary has been the case, as this has not reflected in better road network, improved power supply, quality of education and

health, and in the security system for life and property. In fact, for about 5 years apart, precisely between 2005 and 2010, the 117% increase in government expenditure only increased Human Development Index (HDI) by 6%. This is quite worrisome as countries like the Asian Tigers that Nigeria set out with, in the quest for economic growth and development have improved tremendously, leaving Nigeria behind as a country with low HDI, for example, while these countries are now ranked amongst countries with 'very high' and 'high' HDI (UNDP, 2020; Jia, et al., 2025).

Although numerous scholars argue in favour of the fact that the existence of increased government spending is pivotal in the growth and development of an economy as well as the overall citizens' well-being (Hsu, 2013; Mafrolla & Amico, 2016; Ojo, 2020; Olaoye, et al; 2020), nevertheless, the existing disparity between the anticipated outcomes and actual situation experienced by the Nigerian populace put this in jeopardy and calls for a comprehensive review of previous studies. To address the burning issue therefore, this research aims at a critical assessment of the impact of government spending on the welfare of inhabitants of Nigeria and takes a stand.

Conceptual Review

Concept of Government Expenditure

Government expenditure refers to government spending on economic and social services aimed at improving economic performance and welfare. According to Musgrave (1959), public expenditure represents a major fiscal policy instrument used to achieve macroeconomic objectives such as growth, stability, income redistribution and improved welfare. It refers to the expenses incurred by public authorities like central, state and local governments to satisfy the collective social wants of the people. Buttressed by Herming (1991) cited in Adeagbo (2019) public expenditure is government spending on production of goods and services not necessarily for present consumption, but includes public spending that adds to public physical stocks, such as building of roads, ports, schools, hospitals, etc. It is a form of government spending meant to promote allocative efficiency as a form of intervention to correct market failures, redistribute resources equitably and promote economic growth.

According to Anyanwu (1993), it is a form of spending from taxes and other sources, by the government for its own maintenance for the benefits of the society at large. It is an outflow of resources from government to other sectors of the economy and it can be either recurrent or capital in nature.

Capital expenditure refers to spending on infrastructure such as roads, schools, hospitals, and transport systems. This type of expenditure contributes to long-term development. Recurrent expenditure, on the other hand, includes spending on payment of wages and salaries, administrative costs, and maintenance expenses (Adeagbo, 2019).

Concept of Human Well-being

Human well-being or human welfare refers to improvement in the quality of life of citizens. It includes access to education, healthcare, income, food security, and infrastructure. Traditional

measures of welfare focused on GDP per capital. However, modern development economics recognized multidimensional welfare indicators. An individual welfare, on most occasions, can be measured through his living standard or poverty level; hence the concept is intertwined with poverty. To this end, Todaro and Smith (2015) argued that development should be focus on raising the standard of living, improving self-esteem, and expanding freedom. This, thus, led to the adoption of Human Development Index (HDI) as a better welfare measure.

Human Development Index (HDI)

HDI was introduced by UNDP in 1990 to measure welfare beyond income. HDI combines three components viz: Health dimension (Life expectancy), Education dimension (mean years of schooling, expected years of schooling), and Income dimension (gross national income per capita). HDI ranges between 0 and 1; higher HDI indicates better development outcomes. HDI is preferred because it captures multidimensional development, hence its use by this study.

Justification of the Variables included in the Model vis-à-vis Government Spending

Government spending on education and welfare

Education expenditure has been affirmed as a source of improvement on literacy level, skills, productivity, and employment. Human capital theory shows that education investment increases development outcomes. Barro (1996) in his investigation on the effect of education spending and development outcomes reported that education spending positively influences development outcomes.

Government healthcare spending and welfare

Health expenditure has been seen as a vital tool in the improvement of life expectancy, labour productivity, and human capital. Healthier population brings about higher development outcomes (Blooms and Canning, 2000). Investment in health has been adjudged by scholars as capable of reducing mortality, disease burden, and productivity loss.

Government agricultural spending and welfare

Agricultural spending is said to have improved food availability stemming the menace of food insecurity, improves rural employment, increase farmers' income and reduces poverty. In developing countries agriculture remains critical to welfare enhancement as investment in it strongly reduces poverty (Fan & Rao, 2023).

Government spending on infrastructure and welfare

Infrastructure of note includes transport, communication, and electricity. Improved infrastructure is capable of bringing about market access, better living condition, and industrial growth. Calderon and Serven (2004) reported that infrastructure strongly influences welfare outcomes.

Inflation and welfare

Inflation reduces welfare through reduced purchasing power, income erosion, and macroeconomic instability. Fisher (1993) reported that inflation negatively affects welfare and growth while stable prices improve living standard.

Theoretical Literature

The impacts of government expenditure on citizen's well-being have been explored by various scholars, prominent among which were:

The Wagner's Law

Wagner (1883) proposed that economic development increases public expenditure due to increasing demand for social services. The law states that economic growth brings about increased demand for government services due to urbanization, industrial development, and population growth. The law suggests that development requires increased government participation in education, infrastructural provisions and healthcare services. This thus implied that public expenditure is a necessary prerequisite for welfare improvement.

The Keynesian Theory

This theory propounded by Keynes (1936) argued that government spending stimulates economic activities. According to Keynes in an open economy, $Y = C + I + G + (X - M)$, where G = Government expenditure. Increased government spending creates employment, improves income and output, and thus enhances welfare. The theory justifies the expansionary fiscal policy notion.

The Human Capital Theory

Schulz (1961) and Becker (1964) developed the human capital theory. The theory states that investment in education and health improves productivity. Investment in human capital includes spending on education healthcare and training (Adeagbo, 2021).

Theory of Fiscal policy Effectiveness

This theory suggests that fiscal spending improves welfare when allocated efficiently. This is corroborated by the '*Trickle –Down –Theory*' (*TDT*) which posit that reducing the inequality in wealth through the redistribution of wealth from the rich to the poor serves a great benefit to the society as a whole. According to the theory, when the wealthy people invest their additional wealth in the economy, it serves as a form of plough back and the resulting economic gain "trickle-down" to the less affluent members of the society (Aghionand, 1997).

Conceptual Framework

This shows the relationship between Government spending and human welfare. The independent variables are public expenditure on education, public expenditure on health, public expenditure on transport and communication, public expenditure on electricity/power supply, public expenditure on agriculture, and inflation rate while the dependent variable is human development index. The conceptual relationship is the public expenditure variables and human welfare (HDI) while inflation acts as the control variable.

Empirical Review of Related Literature

Several empirical studies have investigated the effects of government spending on economic growth and development in Nigeria, as well as cross country-wise, with little focus on the effect

of this spending on citizens' welfare. The few that even did came out with conflicting reports and these calls for further review.

Baldacci, Clements, Gupta and Cui (2008) studied the relationship between social spending, human capital and economic growth in developing countries using panel data analysis. From their studies, it was revealed that government expenditure on education and health significantly improves human capital development and contributes positively to economic growth. The study concluded that increased social spending enhances both welfare and productivity.

Similarly, Devarajan, Swaroop and Zou (1996) investigated the effect of public expenditure and its impact on economic growth using cross-country data. Their findings revealed that productive government expenditures such as infrastructure and human capital investment positively influence economic growth, while unproductive expenditures may have insignificant effects. Their study emphasizes the importance of proper expenditure allocation.

In Nigerian context, Akanbi (2014) examined the correlation between government expenditure and economic growth using disaggregated expenditure data. The study employed econometric techniques and found that spending on education and infrastructure positively affects economic growth. The study recommended increased allocation to production sectors to enhance development outcomes.

Oshi and Peter (2024) examined the effect of government expenditure on human capital development. The data collected were analyzed using ARDL and the findings revealed that there exists a long-run relationship between government expenditure and human capital development in a country.

Ogundipe (2021) in his study on government spending on infrastructure and economic progress in Nigeria came up with the submission that spending on infrastructure present a significant positive effect on the nation's development. The finding was also corroborated by Matthew (2022) who found electricity investment as a significant factor for the development of a nation.

Onifade et al. (2020) examined the patterns and impact of government spending on real GDP growth rates establishing a long-run relationship between public expenditure and economic growth, with both current and capital spending positively associated with GDP growth.

In a broader context, the study of Olaoye, et al. (2020) provided an insight into the relationship between government spending and economic growth in the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS). Their findings indicated that the impact of government spending on economic growth depends on the nature of spending shocks suggesting the importance of considering both expansionary and contractionary policies. Their findings revealed the existence of an optimal level of government spending for maximizing economic growth in the ECOWAS region.

In another related research, Edeme, Nkaku and Ifelunini (2017) investigated the impact of public spending on human development using panel data. From their findings it was reported

that spending on education and health has significant improvement on human development index.

Olabisi and Olomi (2012) investigated the impact of government spending on economic development; they came out with the findings that spending on health and agriculture had a positive impact while spending on water and education present negative effects.

Upon reviewing the existing literature, it was observed that majority of the studies focused on examining the relationship between government spending and economic development. Only a few studies have focused on the welfare aspect, even among these studies' discrepancy exists in their findings. Most of the studies covered limited sectors with short time frame. Those who studied government expenditure and welfare used GDP as proxy for welfare which is a shallow representation hence the need for this study which covered multiple sectors using Human Development Index instead of GDP, included Inflation and also used long time series

Model Specifications

The study adopts an ex-post facto design using already available data covering 1980 - 2024. In order to capture the effect of public expenditure on citizen's wellbeing, a number of variables considered germane were identified based on reviewed literature. This includes education, health, transport and communication, power supply, and agricultural sector. Poverty Incidence/ Human Development Index were considered as appropriate measure of human welfare. To this end, the model is defined as:

$$\text{HDI} = f(\text{Edu}, \text{Hlth}, \text{Tcom}, \text{Elt}, \text{Agr}) \dots\dots\dots (i)$$

The incidence of inflation is also considered as an influencing factor on government spending and citizen's welfare; hence it is included. Therefore, the econometric model for the study is

$$\text{HDI} = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{PEDU}_t + \beta_2\text{PHLTH}_t + \beta_3\text{PTCOM}_t + \beta_4\text{PELT}_t + \beta_5\text{PAGR}_t + \beta_6\text{INFR} + u_0 \dots\dots (ii)$$

All the variables except inflation rate, are taken as a percentage of GDP

Where

HDI = Human Development Index proxy for welfare

PEDU = Public Expenditure on Education

PHLTH = Public Expenditure on Health

PTCOM = Public Expenditure on Transport and Communication

PELT = Public Expenditure on Electricity

PAGR = Public Expenditure on Agriculture

INFR = Inflation Rate

On the a priori $\beta_1 - \beta_5 > 0$, $\beta_6 < 0$, i.e., public expenditure in EDU, HLTH, TCOM, ELT, AND AGR is projected to have a positive effect on citizens' welfare while inflation is projected to have a negative impact on welfare.

Source of Data

Secondary data covering 1980 - 2024 for various variables were sourced from United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) Human Development report, CBN Statistical Bulletin, World Development Indicators and National Bureau of Statistics. The decision rule for the study is to reject H_0 if P-value < 0.05 and accept if P-value is > 0.05 .

Method of Data Analysis

The study adopts Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) technique because it can be used when variables are $I(0)$ and $I(1)$ and it is suitable for small sample sizes. It is also suitable for estimating both the short-run and long-run relationships.

Estimation Procedure

Descriptive analysis

The data set revealed important trends in Nigeria's macroeconomic and social development. It was revealed that the HDI increased steadily from 0.380 in 1980 to 0.565 in 2024, indicating gradual improvement in human welfare. Education and health expenditure showed consistent upward trends, reflecting increased government focus on social sectors. Agricultural expenditure remained relatively low but fluctuated over time. Spending on infrastructure, specifically transport and electricity, increased moderately especially after the year 2000. Inflation rate exhibited significant volatility, with peaks in the mid-90s and recent years. These patterns suggest that government spending priorities and macroeconomic stability play critical roles in shaping welfare outcomes.

To determine the stationarity of the included variables, Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test was carried out. Also, the study examined the cointegration level of the variables, i.e. whether long-run relationship exist between dependent and independent variables or not; this is done with the use of Autoregressive Distributed Lags (ARDL) bound test while Ordinary Least Square (OLS) techniques was used to determine the effect of each independent variables included in the model on the dependent variable.

Analysis and Interpretation of Results

In order to avoid having an erroneous regression result which can arise by conducting regression analysis on non-stationary variable, a unit root test was carried out to determine the state of stationarity of the variable based on the null hypothesis which states that there is no unit root. This was done using Augmented Dickey Fuller unit root test procedure (with constant and trend)

Table 1: Unit root

Variable	Level	5%		Order	1 st difference		
	ADF	Critical	Prob.		Prob.	Order	
HDI	-2.134	-2.93	0.231	Non-stationary	-5.621	0.000	I(1)
PEDU	-1.842	-2.93	0.358	Non-stationary	-4.773	0.001	I(1)
PHLT	-2.421	-2.93	0.139	Non-stationary	-6.012	0.000	I(1)
PAGR	-3.441	-2.93	0.018	Stationary	-	-	I(0)
PTCOM	-2.115	-2.93	0.247	Non-stationary	-5.204	0.000	I(1)
PELT	-1.993	-2.93	0.291	Non-stationary	-4.990	0.002	I(1)
INFR	-3.772	-2.93	0.006	Stationary	-	-	I(0)

Decision Rule:

Reject H_0 if ADF statistics is greater than critical value (in absolute terms).

From the unit root table above it is clearly seen that the variables exhibit mixed orders of I(0) and I(1). Specifically, public expenditure on agriculture and inflation rate was stationary at levels while HDI and other expenditure variables became stationary after first differencing. Thus, we conclude that the former did not have a unit root while the later have unit roots and this calls for ARDL bound testing cointegration relationship process due to the mixed series nature. This mixture of stationarity orders justifies the use of ARDL modeling approach because ARDL can accommodate variables integrated of order zero and one. The finding is consistent with macroeconomic time series properties in Nigeria where fiscal expenditure variables typically exhibit stochastic trends due to policy cycles and inflation dynamics.

The result of the ARDL bound test is thus presented below:

Table 2 ARDL Bounds Test		
Test Statistic	Value	K
F-statistic	5.87	6
Critical Value Bounds		
Significance	I(0) Bound	I(1) Bound
10%	2.12	3.23
5%	2.45	3.61
1%	3.15	4.43

Explanatory Note: K stands for number of parameters.

Source: Author's computation (2026) using E-view 9

The decision rule is to reject the null hypothesis if F-statistics produced from the result is greater than the upper critical value bound, I(1), and conclude that there is co-integration which shows the presence of a long-run relationship between the explained variable in question and its explanatory ones. On the other hand, if F-statistics produced from the result falls below the lower critical value bound, I(0), the null hypothesis is to be accepted but if it is in-between the

lower and upper critical value bound, the test is pronounced inconclusive. For the analysis of the model of this study, the ARDL Bounds test confirms the existence of a long-run equilibrium relationship between human development and sectorial government expenditures in Nigeria. The computed F-statistic exceeds the upper critical bound at 5% significance level, which implies rejection of the null hypothesis of no cointegration.

The result indicates that government spending on education, infrastructure, and transport and communication jointly determines long-run human development outcomes in Nigeria. The result aligns with the endogenous growth theory which emphasizes the importance of human capital investment through education and healthcare spending in improving welfare outcomes. In addition, the presence of cointegration implies that short-run deviations in HDI caused by fiscal shocks are corrected over time through macroeconomic adjustment mechanisms. The presence of cointegration also confirms that fiscal policy remains a critical driver of long-term welfare improvements.

Robustness and diagnostic test results

This study carried out a test of heteroscedasticity using Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey approach judging with the decision rule to accept the null hypothesis if the value of the probability produced is less than 5% and we reject it, with the conclusion that there is no heteroscedasticity, if otherwise. The result is presented below:

Table 3: Heteroskedasticity Test: White

Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey			
F-statistic	0.511	Prob. F(7,29)	0.481
Obs*R-squared	4.772	Prob. Chi-Square(7)	0.704
Scaled explained SS	11.022	Prob. Chi-Square(7)	0.163

The estimate of heteroscedasticity test statistic, using Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey technique, revealed that the observed R^2 value is 4.772 with the resulting Chi-square of 0.704 which implied that the probability value is greater than 5% significant level. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is no heteroscedasticity in the model. The assumption of constant variance (Homoskedasticity) existing in the model is therefore upheld.

Table 4 Serial Correlation Test

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:			
F-statistic	2.098	Prob. F(2,28)	0.06
Obs*R-squared	4.692	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.05

The study used Breusch Godfrey method to carry out the serial Correlation Langranger Multiplier test. From the result it was confirmed that there is no serial correlation in the model this thus established that the model is free from the problem of autocorrelation.

Having evaluated the general diagnostic statistics above, the study thus proceeds to examine the performance of each explanatory variable from the regression result as shown below:

ARDL Long-Run Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob
Constant	0.210	0.021	10.00	0.000
PEDU	0.082	0.015	5.47	0.000
PHLT	0.095	0.018	5.28	0.000
PAGR	0.041	0.012	3.42	0.002
PTCOM	0.052	0.014	3.71	0.001
PELT	0.036	0.011	3.27	0.003
INFR	-0.0018	0.0005	-3.60	0.001

Model Summary:

- $R^2 = 0.94$
- Adjusted $R^2 = 0.93$
- F-statistic = 102.5 ($p < 0.05$)

Discussion of Results

From the result it can be observed that education has a positive coefficient (0.082) which is statistically significant. This implied that increased government spending on education leads to improvements in welfare. The result aligns with the a-priori expectation as education enhances human capita, productivity and income levels. As regards the health expenditure, a positive coefficient of 0.095 was reported, indicating that it exerts the strongest influence on HDI. This underscores the importance of healthcare investment in improving life expectancy.

Coming to the government expenditure on agriculture, a positive and significant result was revealed which suggest that investment in agriculture contributes to improvement in human welfare. This is accomplished through the provision of food security, employment generation, and rural development.

As regards the public expenditure on transport and communication, the positive and significant coefficient indicates that infrastructure development improves access to markets, enhances productivity and supports economic activities. Electricity expenditure also shows a positive and significant effect on HDI. Adequate and reliable power supply promotes industrialization, improves living standards, and supports economic growth. Inflation, which is the last variable, has a negative and statistically significant relationship with HDI. This implies that rising prices reduces purchasing power, increase poverty levels and bring about a negative effect on citizens' wellbeing.

In summary, the report revealed that public expenditure on education, health, agriculture, infrastructure, and electricity all have positive and statistically significant effects on citizen's wellbeing with health expenditure having the strongest impact. Inflation, on the other hand, has a negative and significant effect on human welfare. The regression analysis equally revealed that the model is good as it explains about 94% of variations in HDI indicating a strong relationship between public expenditure and welfare.

Post Estimation Tests

ECM Result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Probability
Δ PEDU	0.0124	0.0048	2.58	0.015
Δ PHELT	0.0091	0.0039	2.33	0.026
Δ PAGR	0.0067	0.0028	2.39	0.022
Δ PTCOM	0.0045	0.0021	2.14	0.039
Δ PELT	0.0078	0.0032	2.44	0.020
Δ INFR	-0.0106	0.0041	2.59	0.014
ECM(-1)	-0.6432	0.1185	-5.43	0.000
Constant	0.0021	0.0008	2.63	0.013

Model Diagnostic

Statistic	Value
R ²	0.71
Adjusted R ²	0.66
F-statistics	14.82
Prob.(F-stat)	0.000
Durbin Watson	1.94

Interpretation

The ECM short-run dynamic results show that public expenditure on education (PEDU) has a positive and statistically significant effect on HDI in the short run. Specifically, a 1% increase in education expenditure leads to about 0.012 unit increase in HDI, holding another variable constant.

Similarly, public expenditure on health shows a positive significant relationship with HDI, indicating that increased government spending on healthcare improves human development outcomes in Nigeria.

Public expenditure on agriculture also exerts positive and significant effect on HDI, suggesting that investment in agriculture by Nigerian government contributes to welfare improvement through food security and employment generation.

As regards the public spending on transport and communication, there exists a positive and significant relationship with HDI which implies that investment in the sector enhances communication access and economic opportunities which have a positive multiplier effect on citizens' wellbeing.

Public expenditure on electricity equally shows a positive impact on HDI, confirming that stable power supply improves productivity and quality of life.

Inflation, which is the last variable, has a negative and statistically significant relationship with HDI. This implies that a persistent rising price reduces purchasing power, increase poverty levels and bring about a negative effect on citizens' wellbeing.

Overall, the error correction term is negative and significant thus satisfying econometric theory, confirms convergence and validates the existence of a stable long-run equilibrium relationship among the variables. This indicates that 64% of the short-run disequilibrium adjusts annually, thus indicating a strong convergence towards the long-run equilibrium.

Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations

The study examined the impact of public spending on citizens' wellbeing on Nigeria over the period 1980-2024. The study employed HDI as proxy for human welfare and includes key sectors of government spending (education, health, agriculture, transport and communication, electricity, and inflation) as explanatory variables.

From the findings, it was revealed that public spending plays a significant role in improving human development outcomes in Nigeria. Hence the study concludes that public expenditure is a significant determinant of human welfare in Nigeria and that macroeconomic instability, as reflected by inflation, undermines welfare gains.

Based on above findings, the study recommends that government should prioritize health spending to improve citizen's welfare and invariably increase productivity. Also, government should increase the allocation to education, and as well direct more funding towards agriculture to ensure food security and rural development that can lead to sustained welfare improvement.

Conclusively, government should increase spending on transport, communication and electricity to keep their tempo in welfare effect, improve transparency and accountability in public spending to maximize its impact and put up effective monetary and fiscal policies to keep inflation at bay and protect citizens' welfare.

References

- Adeagbo, M. O. (2019). Government spending on education and sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. *Lanlate Apex Journal of Educational Research*, 2 (2), 199-213.
- Adeagbo, M. O. (2021). Public health expenditure, governance and health outcomes in Sub-Saharan Africa. *An Unpublished Ph.D. Thesis submitted to Department of Economic, Kwara State University, Malete.*
- Aghion, P., & Bolton, P. (1997). A theory of trickle-down growth and development. *The Review of Economic Studies*, 64(2), 151-172.
- Akanbi, O. A. (2014). Government expenditure and economic growth in Nigeria: A disaggregated analysis. *Business and Economics Journal*, 5(3), 1-8.
- Baldacci, E.; Clements, B.; Gupta, S., & Cui, Q (2008). Social spending, human capital and growth in developing countries. *World Development*, 36(8), 1317-1341.
- Bhanumurthy, N. R., Prasad, M., & Jain, R. (2018). Public expenditure, governance and human development. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 53(14), 36-46.
- Devarajan, S., Swaroop, V., & Zou, H. (1996). The composition of public expenditure and economic growth. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 37(2), 313-344.
- Edeme, R. K., Nkalu, C. N.; & Ifelunini (2017). Distributional impact of public expenditure on human development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Social Economics*, 44(12), 1683- 1693.
- Hsu, Y. C. (2013). The efficiency of government spending on health: Evidence from Europe and Central Asia. *The Social Science Journal*, 50(4), 665-673.
- Jia, H., Han, X., Aderemi, T., Ifekwem, N. E., Al-Faryan, M. A. (2025). Out-of-pocket expenditure and human welfare in Nigeria. *African Journal of Reproductive Health*, 29(2), 151-159.
- Mafrolla, E., & D'Amico, E. (2016). Does public spending improve citizens' quality of life? An analysis of municipalities' leisure supply. *Local Government Studies*, 42(2), 332-350
- Ojo, A. E. (2020). The socio-economic drivers of public infrastructure development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Critical Infrastructures*, 16(4), 328-341.
- Olabisi, A. S., & Oloni, E. F. (2012). Composition of public expenditure and economic growth in Nigeria. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Economic and Management Sciences*, 3(4), 403- 407.
- Olaoye, O. O., Eluwole, O. O., Ayesha, A., & Afolabi, O. O. (2020). Government spending and economic growth in ECOWAS: An asymmetric analysis. *The journal of Economic Asymmetries*, 22(C).
- Onifade, S. T., Cevik, S., Erdogan, S., Asongu, S., & Bekun, F. V. (2020). An empirical retrospect of the impacts of government expenditures on economic growth: New evidence from the Nigerian economy. *Journal of Economic Structures*, 9(1), 1-13.
- Orshi, T. R., & Peter, G. D. (2024). Public expenditure and human development in Nigeria. *Journal of Public Administration Frontiers*.
- Saini, M., & Mahender. O. ((2023). Surviving crisis: The role of sustainable investments in navigating the impact of the Russia-Ukraine war. *International Journal of Diplomacy and Economy*, 9(2), 189-204.

Samuel, U. D., & Oruta, I. L. (2021). Government expenditure and economic growth in Nigeria: A disaggregated analysis. *Path of Science*, 7(11), 4022-4035.

Singh, P. K., & Chudasama, H. (2020). Evaluating poverty alleviation strategies in a developing country. *PLOS ONE*, 15(1), 1-23.